
Research

Study of consumers' satisfaction regarding Fast-food restaurants in Cameroon

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Abstract: The main objective of this research is to investigate consumer satisfaction in the context of the booming fast-food industry of Cameroon. More precisely, we break the satisfaction concept into different constructs, atmosphere satisfaction, menu satisfaction, and global satisfaction, based on the different drivers of satisfaction; we then evaluate the influence of atmosphere satisfaction and menu satisfaction on global satisfaction as well as the impact of the three dimensions of satisfaction on consumers' loyalty. Furthermore, we evaluated the moderator role of global satisfaction on the relationship linking atmosphere and menu satisfaction to loyalty. The study results indicated that fast-food menus and atmosphere satisfaction have a positive effect on global satisfaction. As well, out of the three dimensions of satisfaction, global and menu satisfaction proved to have a positive impact on consumer loyalty, but the effect of the atmosphere satisfaction proves to be not determinant. In addition, the mediator role of global satisfaction proved to be relevant.

Keywords: Consumers, Satisfaction, Fast-food, Cameroon

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1. Introduction

There have been abundant researches investigating consumer satisfaction in the services industry. For over forty years, an increasing interest has aroused on consumers' satisfaction regarding services. Many authors have contributed to the advancement of the research; namely Howard and Sheth (1969); Ltifi and Ghardi (2012). Ekinci and Sirakaya (2004), Cadotte and Turgeon (1988), and Bartikowski and Llosa (2004), or more recently the work of Cameliset al. (2017) highlighted the different interactions affecting the degree of customer satisfaction,

The attention directed to the service industry, such as fast-food, is due to the improvement in the level of consumer satisfaction, driven by the increasing importance of that sector. It is worth mentioning that, in that industry,

differentiation is required to gain market shares, as the industry products are highly homogeneous, and the firms can only compete through service quality maximization.

Many studies have directed their attention to the importance of service quality on consumers' satisfaction and loyalty. However, most of these studies were based on developed and emerging countries but not on sub-Saharan African countries; furthermore, these works did not consider the different components of satisfaction (Soriano 2012; Ladharai et al. 2017; Ajina et al. 2015). Hence, this research investigated consumer satisfaction in the context of the booming fast-food industry of Cameroon.

More precisely, we decomposed the satisfaction concept into three constructs based on the different drivers: atmosphere satisfaction, menu satisfaction and global satisfaction. We then evaluated the influence of atmosphere and menu satisfaction on global satisfaction and the impact of the three dimensions of satisfaction on consumers' loyalty. The researchers also evaluated the moderator's roles of global satisfaction in the relationships linking the atmosphere and menu satisfaction to loyalty.

The study result indicated that the fast-food menu and atmosphere satisfaction positively affect global satisfaction. As well, out of the three dimensions of satisfaction, global and menu satisfaction proved to have a positive impact on consumer loyalty, but the effect of the atmosphere satisfaction proved to be not determinant. In addition, the mediator role of global satisfaction proved to be relevant.

The remaining of this document is as follows. After presenting a brief literature review on the satisfaction construct, we developed the hypothesis and the conceptual model. The methodology is then presented before moving to the presentation of results. Finally, a conclusion and recommendations are proposed.

2. Literature Review

Research on consumers' satisfaction has made significant progress recently in terms of insightful results produced. The subject is even considered as being the cornerstone of marketing, as argued by Peterson and Wilson (1992) and Cova and Petre (2006). Originally, the construct of satisfaction emanated from the labor field and was defined as "a way of rewarding an individual for a job" Homans(1961), it is above all the work of Howard and Sheth (1969) or even Oliver (1980) who introduced this construct to the marketing field. From now on, satisfaction can be glimpsed from different points of view. Hence, some researches have defined satisfaction as a result of consumption experience (Cardozo 1965; Oliver 2014; Evrard2016). Other studies have related the concept of satisfaction more closely with consumer behavior, Mihaela (2015). Finally, Oliver (2010) suggests a four-step process leading to satisfaction. According to that author, satisfaction is related to three constructs: performance, expectations and dis-confirmation. This last contribution gives the construct of satisfaction an emotional dimension and makes its theoretical contribution one of the first explanatory models of this dimension in marketing.

2.1 The transactional approach of satisfaction

Many studies have defined satisfaction from the transactional perspective. In that approach, satisfaction is considered as "a subsequent state inherent to a specific transaction, limited in time" Audrain-Pontevia (2016). A similar definition was already proposed by, Lee and Kim (2017) by including perception and stating that "customer satisfaction measures the perception of what he actually enjoys from goods or service consumption, in comparison with his expected satisfaction when consuming similar goods or service. In other words, the proponents of this approach suggest that the consumer assesses goods or services from the experience gained from their consumption; the latter measuring satisfaction by the difference between the experience and its initial expectations Javed and Cheema (2017). Faced with this static approach, which only considers the consumer experience toward the product or service provider; another perspective is based on the relational approach. According to Ngobo (2017), the measurement of satisfaction

from a relational perspective is defined as a “continuous global evaluation of the ability of the company or the brand to provide the benefits sought by the customer”. Hence, many viewpoints need to be accounted for when defining satisfaction. This is what Garbarino and Johnson (2008) highlighted when describing satisfaction as “a cumulative construct, summing up satisfaction gained from specific products or services of the company”. This is a more recent approach to measure the consumer satisfaction construct.

2.2 Satisfaction in the restaurant industry

There have been abundant researches investigating consumer satisfaction in the restaurant industry. Among them, the study by Soriano (2019) based on a sample of 3,872 consumers, concluded that the most important determinants of the consumer choice of a restaurant were the food quality, namely freshness of the product, shape, variety of menus and quantity of food served; as well as the service quality price, and the atmosphere of the restaurant. These dimensions provide insight into the most relevant factors of consumer loyalty in relation to their degree of satisfaction.

Suhartanto et al. (2019) also revealed the relationship between the traditional constructs on which satisfaction is defined, namely; food quality, atmosphere, quality of facilities and the likelihood of visiting the restaurant by consumers. The food quality was found significantly to influence the respondent behavior toward returning to the restaurant in the same study.

In a cross-cultural analysis applied on a sample of 5136 consumers from 4 different countries (Scotland, Jamaica, United States and Wales), Omar et al. (2016) evaluated the satisfaction of fast-food restaurant chains (McDonald's, Burger King, KFC, etc.). Their study finding revealed that, the consumer satisfaction was mainly driven by the relationship with the restaurant staff as well as the quality of the facilities. Menvielle (2006), meanwhile, evaluated the different variables of satisfaction and the consumer loyalty, using a sample of 262 consumers in the Quebec region, the study finding revealed that, food quality explains the consumer's likelihood of returning to the restaurant. The results are in line with the finding by Tripathi (2017) that the food quality is an important determinant explaining consumer satisfaction in restaurant.

Jalil et al. (2016) made a ranking of the key factors influencing the consumer satisfaction of in the hospitality industry. Their study results indicate that the critical factors determining the consumer satisfaction were found to be the courtesy of staff, the price, and the food quality, however, their study did not provide evidence of impact of the environmental factors.

From the above development, we can conclude that consumer satisfactions are apprehended by many variables that we will be including in our conceptual framework.

3. A conceptual model and hypotheses of consumer satisfactions

Our conceptual model is based on the relational approach, which aim is to understand which dimensions of satisfaction matters the most to consumers and motivate them to eat in fast food. To this end, we have divided the relationships between a consumer and the service provider into three stages:

1. A pre-transactional stage based on consumer choice and decision-making criteria.
2. A transactional stage during which there is an exchange between the two parties and an assessment of tangible aspects by the consumer.
3. A post-transaction step, allowing the consumer to make an assessment of their experience and to estimate the degree of fragmentation of the restaurant in the future.

The pre-transaction stage refers to the initial approach that a consumer follows in the purchasing relationship with a company. Before any relationship, the consumer assesses the value he can benefit from the relationship that links him

with the service provider. Thus, the consumer identifies some key elements that will allow him to assess the quality of the product that will be offered to him later in the relationship. This is how the sound environment or the decoration comes into play at this level. According to some authors, they even constitute a fairly significant element of differentiation from the competition (Belman 2004; Pratminingsih et al. 2018). Finally, the waiting time before being able to sit down to eat, is as well, according to Soriano (2002), a critical factor for choosing a restaurant or not.

Regarding the transactional stage, the consumer must make choices of the menus while considering the best quality/price ratio to properly evaluate the service provided by the fast-food. The food quality and the freshness are crucial elements determining the consumers' return to the restaurant, Nadzirah et al. (2013). Although many of the studies conducted in the hospitality industry have been emphasizing indoor restaurant service quality, it is also worth mentioning that the delivery service quality is a major factor determining customer satisfaction in the fast-food restaurant. Hence, similar to Soriano (2002) we also consider that dimension in this stage. Finally, the other aspects that we can consider in this transactional stage concern the price-quality ratio of the menu. Offering a quality menu is not enough to achieve consumer satisfaction; it also needs to be in line with the price and restaurant atmosphere or cleanliness (Soriano, 2002). Consumers are looking for value and constantly desire higher value for their desired menu Klara (2012).

We thus formulate the hypothesis that:

- **H1: Consumer satisfaction toward the fast-food menu positively influences the global satisfaction**

As already said, consumers assess the value of the benefit they enjoy from eating in fast-food restaurants. This assumption allows one to make an idea of the quality of the product that will be offered to him. This is how the restaurant atmosphere; decoration plays a key role at this level. According to Liljander and Strandvik (2020) the emotional variables associated with the restaurant atmosphere create an emotion in the consumers that will affect their satisfaction level. Some researchers demonstrate that emotional variables can even constitute a fairly significant element of differentiation from the competition (Belman 1996; Chen 2014). Hence, we posit that

- **H2: Satisfaction toward the restaurant atmosphere positively influences the global satisfaction**

Similar to the relational approach to satisfaction, we measured the effects of satisfaction on loyalty. More precisely, we refer to the work of Soriano (2002), Sulek and Hensley (2004), Gilbert et al. (2004), Menvielle (2006), and Andaleed and Conway (2006). These works provide evidence supporting that, the more consumers are satisfied with the service provider, the more likely they will come back to him. This long-term relationship has also been proven in the marketing empirical literature (Anderson and Sullivan 1993; Tanveer and Lodhi 2016; Yi 1997). We also consider these elements in the post-transaction stage and two dimensions were thus proposed, namely the probability of returning to the restaurant and the probability of recommending the restaurant. These considerations allowed us to formulate the following set of hypotheses:

- **H3: Satisfaction toward the menu positively influences loyalty**
- **H4: Satisfaction toward the restaurant atmosphere has a positive influence on loyalty**
- **H5: Global satisfaction has a positive influence on loyalty**

Finally, we also consider the possible moderating role plays by the overall satisfaction on the relationship between consumer satisfaction, and loyalty, namely, we posit that:

- **H6.a Global satisfaction is a mediator in the relationship between satisfaction toward the menu and royalty**
- **H6.b Global satisfaction is a mediator in the relationship between satisfaction regarding the company atmosphere and loyalty**

From the above development, we provide the representation of both the transactional approach representation and the conceptual model.

Figure 1: The transactional approach representation

Our research model therefore considers all these dimensions from a relational approach and is presented as follow

Figure 2: Conceptual Model

4. Methodology/Empirical Analysis

Our study objective was achieved using data collected from a survey. Precisely, we used a self-administrated questionnaire online and offline to collect data from some college students in Cameroon. The selection of students as target population was driven by the fact that, they constitute one of the major segments in the fast-food in Cameroon. From this data collection process, we were also able to test the conceptual model using a sample of 621 students. The measuring scales were designed following the procedure of Churchill (1979). For our exploratory phase, we as well generated a set of items by referring to the existing literature, namely pre-existing scales taken from the literature on consumer satisfaction and loyalty in the fast-food industry. The measurement scales used in this research are similar to those adopted by Gilbert et al. (2004) who investigated the consumer satisfaction in the fast-food industry.

Before testing the hypothesis, we first performed the internal consistency analysis using the Cronbach test, we also applied the exploratory factor analysis. The objective of this analysis was to investigate how closely related are the set of items found in each construct, and to reduce the data into a smaller set of summary variables, before making the regression analysis. The Varimax rotation based on the maximization of the correlation coefficients of the most correlated variables was suitable in our case since the regression assumes the independence of the explanatory variables Hair et al. (1998). We refer to the Kaiser's rule to determine the number of factors to extract Kaiser (1958). Hence, only the factors whose eigenvalue was greater than 1 were retained. The percentage of explained variance ensures that the factors explain a minimum of variance. In social sciences, the minimum percentage variance should be 60% Hair et al. (1998). As for the explanatory factor analysis, the minimum variance threshold for interpreting the factors is 0.3 (Gorsuch 1974; Leary 1995).

In the tables presenting the loading of the items on each factor, we only presented the loading greater than 0.30 for reliability. We retained the items strongly correlated with a single factor and whose factorial weight was greater or equal to 0.5. Items with commonality less than 0.5 were eliminated by successive iterations.

Regarding the different dimensions of satisfaction and overall satisfaction, the respondents were asked to give the opinion on their satisfaction regarding the fast-food. Based in the Likert scale of 1 to 5 (1-not satisfied at all, 5-very satisfied). As well, concerning the behavioral intentions, the respondents were asked to give their opinion on the likelihood of returning to the fast-food or recommending the fast food to someone in the near future, we also used the Likert scale of 1 to 5 (1-not at all likely, 5-very likely).

The internal consistency analysis of the model was validated by the Cronbach's alpha test. The results of this internal consistency (ACP, Cronbach test and Varimax) are shown in the bellow (table 1).

Table 1: Internal Consistency Analysis Results

Sn	Items	F1	F2
1	Waiting time	693	
2	Helpfulness	610	
3	Variety of menus	539	
4	Food quality Health aspects	541	479
5	-Product freshness	372	566
6	menu presentation	683	
7	Food quantity	617	387
8	Menu price ratio	676	
9	Promotions	514	
10	Music		715
11	Cleanliness	505	413
12	Decoration		773
13	Frequentative		751
14	Global atmosphere		675
15	Eigen value	5,148	1,611
16	Variance	34,918	10,681
17	Alpha de Cronbach	0,692	0,693

The alpha value must be at least 0.7 for confirmatory factor analysis, Hair et al. (1998). In the case of exploratory factor analysis, it is considered acceptable if it is between 0.5 and 0.7 Nunnally (1978). We have therefore adopted a minimum threshold of 0.5.

The principal component analysis of the different dimension of satisfaction, performed using SPSS 13.0, revealed a two-dimensional structure, accounting for more than 45% of the total variance at the global level. Precisely, the analysis suggests that, the satisfaction coming from the restaurant menu account for (34.988% of total explained variance), while the satisfaction due to the restaurant atmosphere represents (10.671% of total explained variance).

Similarly, the internal consistency of the constructs related to global satisfaction and reliability (loyalty) was also performed through successive iterations scales. From this process, we retain one-dimensional structure of each of the scales considered. However, this approach has led to the removal of many items with poor loading. The constructs related to the overall satisfaction and loyalty has also been represented by two items.

We also examined the possible relationship between the different dimensions of satisfaction, global satisfaction as well as loyalty, in this case, the internal consistency was evaluated through the computation of rho proposed by Jöreskog (1971). As well, the exploratory factor analysis also supports the reliability of our constructs with indices greater than 0.65 (Table 2).

Table 2: Reliability of the Constructs

Item/category	Alpha de Cronbach (nbd'items)	Rhò de Joreskog
Menu. Sat	0,662 (4 items)	0,673
Atmosphere. Sat	0,691 (3 items)	0,664
Global Sat	0,752 (2 items°)	0,754
Loyalty	0,809 (2 items)	0,727

4.1 Hypothesis Testing

From our conceptual model, we were supposed to investigate two issues: the influences of the different dimensions of satisfaction on the overall satisfaction and loyalty, as well as the possible moderating role of overall satisfaction on the relationships between the dimensions of post-transaction satisfaction and loyalty. The results of the regressions analysis indicates that, there is a positive and significant impact of the two dimensions of pre-transactional satisfaction (satisfaction coming from the menu offered and the restaurant atmosphere) on overall satisfaction. This is in line with the assumptions made that, overall satisfaction is mainly explained by pre-transaction satisfaction with attributes related to the menu proposed and the fast-food atmosphere. Hypotheses H1 and H2 are therefore validated.

The analysis results also show a significant positive influence of overall satisfaction on loyalty, which supports the existing literature results. Finally, the research outcome revealed some influence of the components of pre-transaction satisfaction on loyalty. Precisely, the results indicate that the satisfaction resulting from the restaurant atmosphere has no significant influence on loyalty.

- While the satisfaction resulting from the menu offered positively and significantly affects loyalty

Table 3: Results of Hypothesis test

Independent Variables	Influence of	Coefficient	total	Sig.	Conclude
Global Satisfaction	Sat menu	0,386	6,909	0,019	S
Global Satisfaction	Sat Atmosphere	0,193	3,867	0,021	S
Loyalty	Global Satisfaction	0,717	14,418	0,022	S
Loyalty	Sat Atmosphere	-0,045	-1,0664	0,246	NS
Loyalty	Sat Menu	0,244	4,806	0,013	S

To expand our analysis, we sought to understand the possible moderating nature of overall satisfaction on the relationships between the dimensions of satisfaction and loyalty. The literature indicated that satisfaction has proven to be considered a good predictor of loyalty Mencarelli et al. (2010); Orji (2013); Howard and Huang (2010); Newman and Werbel(1973); Engel, Blackwell and Kollat (1978). Walters Achour suggested a positive theoretical relationship between satisfaction and loyalty. He also provides evidence supporting a link between satisfaction and loyalty (Achour 2006). Regarding the hospitality industry Dimitriadis (2006) and Gilbert et al. (2004) demonstrate the existence of the relationship between satisfaction and loyalty

Therefore, the mediating role of global satisfaction was tested using the three-step procedure of Baron and Kenny (1986), which uses three independent regression analyses. This approach proves the existence of mediation by demonstrating that:

- The independent variables affect the mediator,
- The independent variables have a significant effect on the dependent variables,
- The mediator influences the dependent variable.

In other words, the path between independent and dependent variables should be less significant than the path between the mediator and the independent variables. Mediation is considered total when the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable disappears entirely in the presence of the mediating variable and that between the mediator and the dependent variables remains highly significant.

When the influence of the mediator on the independent variable is simply insignificant, we are then in the case of partial mediation. In cases of partial mediation, only part of the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable is exerted through the mediating variable and the other part is exerted directly on the independent variable or, possibly through another variable not considered in the model.

From the previous analysis, we established that the two dimensions of satisfaction significantly and positively influence overall satisfaction, our mediating variable. The latter positively and significantly influences loyalty, which stands for the dependent variable.

Concerning the direct influences of the dimensions of satisfaction on the dependent variable, we previously observed differentiated effects according to the explanatory variable considered; namely,

- The satisfaction deriving from the restaurant atmosphere has no significant influence on loyalty; hence we can conclude that there is a total mediating role of global satisfaction on the relationship linking satisfaction towards the atmosphere and loyalty:
- Satisfaction coming from menus has a significant and positive influence on loyalty.
- We tested a possible partial mediation via overall satisfaction. The test results revealed that overall satisfaction is a partial mediator in the atmosphere satisfaction–loyalty relationship.

According to Fornell, Lorange and Roos (1990), the total effect of one variable on another is the sum of the direct and indirect effects. The analysis of the total effects revealed that overall satisfaction is the variable that exerts the strongest influence on loyalty. It is also worth mentioning that satisfaction from the menu has a strong positive influence on loyalty, both directly and indirectly, via overall satisfaction.

4.2 Goodness of the fit

The size of our overall sample (621 individuals) allows us to use the structural equation method to test our hypotheses of direct links between variables. With this in mind, we used the Amos 4.0 software, with estimation by the maximum likelihood method and bootstrap procedure on 200 replications, to ensure the robustness of the results obtained.

Confirmatory factor analysis leads to confronting empirical data with hypotheses on the relationships between observed variables and latent variables Evrard, Pras and Roux (2009). With this in mind, we selected certain indices that reflect the extent of the adjustment (adjustment indices) or the lack of adjustment (residuals) of the model N'Goala (2003).

Given the size of our sample (n= 621), and based on the recommendations of literature, we used the following indices to perform the goodness of fit analysis.

The Normed fit index (NFI), the Non-Normed fit index (NNFI), or the Tucker lewis index (TLI), the identity leadership inventory (ILI), and Cooperative fit index (CFI). It is generally desirable that they be greater than 0.9 when the sample size exceeds 250 (Bollen and Long 1993; Hu and Bentler1995).

We also relied on Gamma 1, Gamma 2, RMR and RMSEA and Chi-square/ degree of freedom indices to check the adjustment of the models tested. We decided not to retain neither the Chi-square, which is too sensitive to the size of the sample, nor the GFI and AGFI indices, considered less reliable than the Gamma1 and Gamma2 indices, because they are too sensitive to the number of parameters to be estimated Roussel and al. (2002).

The Chi² value adjusted according to the number of degrees of freedom (Chi²/dof) must generally be less than 5. It is advisable to carefully observe the residuals, especially the RMSEA, to have a more precise indication of the degree of freedom adjustment between the theoretical model and the data (Browne and Cudeck 1993; Hu and Bentle 1995). The RMSEA is considered suitable when it is close to 0.05, acceptable below 0.08, and unacceptable above 0.1 Browne and Cudeck (1993). These elements are presented in table 4 below.

Table 4: the direct, indirect and total effect

Impact on loyalty	Direct Effect	Indirect Effect	Total Effect
Sat Menu	0,243	0,277	0,520
Sat Atmosphere	-0,044	0,13725	0,093
Global Satisfaction	0,716		0,716

On sight, if these thresholds, the fitness of the model is satisfactory. Indeed, the adjustment indicators (NFI=0.988, NNFI=0.979, CFI = 0.966; IFI = 0.976; TLI = 0.948) all exceed the threshold of 0.9 and the RMSEA value is also very suitable (0.043) as indicated below in table 5.

Table 5: Post estimation analysis

	Chi-Square		Gamma 2	RMR	RMSEA	NFI	NNFI	Chi ² /ddl	IFI	TLI	CFI
Threshold		>0,9	>0,9	< 0,1	<0,08	>0,9	>0,9	< 5	>0,9	>0,9	>0,9

Results	124,78	0,988	0,979	0,049	0,043	0,948	0,949	3,299	0,976	0,948	0,966
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5. Conclusion

Through this research, we wanted to study consumer satisfaction regarding Cameroon's fast-food industry and the dimensions that can explain consumer satisfaction when visiting a fast-food type restaurant. The study result indicated that fast-food menus and atmosphere satisfaction positively affect global satisfaction. As well, out of the three dimensions of satisfaction, global and menu satisfaction proved to have a positive impact on consumer loyalty, but the effect of the atmosphere satisfaction appeared to be not determinant. In addition, the mediator role of global satisfaction proved to be relevant. As for the factors influencing satisfaction in general, food appeared to be the most crucial dimension when consumers evaluate the satisfaction attached to the meal, over the other factors. Our contribution is innovative insofar as it extrapolates the studies on consumer satisfaction that we mentioned in our literature review. We brought to light new dimensions, particularly the importance of the fast-food atmosphere, and validated almost all the hypotheses evoked. Therefore, we can affirm that our contribution should be useful for other studies that corroborate our assertions. These results deepen the conclusions of some previous studies (in restaurants with service) by insisting more on the concepts attached to food (quality, quantity of food).

Finally, regarding loyalty, we confirmed that it was strongly linked to overall satisfaction. Moreover, loyalty is explained more by attitudinal loyalty (recommendation of the restaurant) than by behavioral loyalty (return to the restaurant).

Be that as it may, in light of these results, consumers seem to have become aware of an important and rapidly expanding phenomenon in Africa, and the search for quality food is now becoming a major dimension. Therefore, fast-food companies in Cameroon need to sharpen their services' quality to improve consumers' satisfaction in all aspects and guarantee their loyalty.

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